

A Review of Flood Hazard Planning, Management and Mapping within the Context of Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Flash flooding in Saudi Arabia, is one of the most devastating hazards in terms of loss of human lives, damage of property assets and disruption to businesses. The paper examines current practices of disaster management, planning, and mapping in Saudi Arabia. Various management and mapping issues are highlighted, aiming at exploring critical points of concern in order to outline an appropriate approach to deal with flash flooding disaster. The main recommendations are: (1) effectively involve local stakeholders and populations in the management process and make use of accumulated community knowledge; (2) develop tools to identify and map areas potentially at risk; (3) ensure data availability of appropriate volume and quality; (4) improve coordination and cooperation among various local institutions; and (5) establish either national or local centers for hazard emergencies entrusted with all required tasks towards effective disaster management and mapping using state of the art technologies.

Key words: Natural disasters, Flash flooding, Disaster management and Mapping, Saudi Arabia.

INTRODUCTION

There has been an increased interest in disaster planning and management in recent decades, so much so that the United Nations declared the 1990s, the International Decade for Natural Disaster Reduction (IDNDR). All over the world, disasters are becoming more frequent and more devastating. Saudi Arabia is not an exception to this phenomenon. A recent UN study asserted that natural disasters at the global level have doubled since 1980, but in the Middle East and North Africa, they have increased threefold (iNewsArabia, 2013). This conclusion should warrant local planners and managers to take seriously the issue of flood hazards in this part of the world.

As far as Saudi Arabia is concerned, flash flooding resulting from torrential rainfall is the most common type of flooding. Although the country is characterized by an arid and semi-arid climate with fluctuating low rainfall (less than 150 mm per year), it has recently witnessed some recurring devastating flash flood events. The city of Jeddah, for example recorded in September 2009 a rainfall amount of 150 mm for only four hours of continuous pouring rain. Such rainfall unseen for more than 25 years, has led to huge flooding with 120 deaths and thousands of injured people and damaged properties, let alone other incurred costs estimated at billions of dollars. Even a rainfall amount of 32 mm, which is most ordinary in many parts of the world, resulted in Riyadh on November 2013 in some deaths, severe damages to properties and disruptions to city life and educational institutions.

The aim of this paper is to examine the process of disaster planning and management as actually practiced in Saudi Arabia. Issues of management, planning and mapping of urban flood hazards are described. The institutional and legislative framework to address them is explained. The paper describes and discusses the planning and management procedures commonly adopted in dealing with urban flood hazards according to the four phases of disaster management and planning process; namely mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. The comparison between what is being actually done and what should be done may help identify deficiencies in current practices and suggest thereof corrections towards a better and more effective flood risk management, planning and mapping.

Flood Hazard Management: The Institutional and Legal Framework

The General Directorate of Civil Protection (GDPC) under the auspices of Civil Defense Department (CDD) is the authority responsible for disaster management in Saudi Arabia. Its mandate includes legislation, regulation, implementation, and coordination between different government agencies. In times of disaster, warning messages are sent to the public through different communication means. The Local Emergency Committee (LEC) leads civil protection efforts at the local provincial level. Every local government department is represented within the LEC which convenes whenever necessary to discuss, plan or propose whatever required in terms of administrative procedures, measures or action plans. It also defines the role assigned to each department or sector and lists the available public and private means and how they can be brought into use. To be always prepared to face up to the challenges of disaster events, the GDPC conducts, though not regularly, various training, workshops and conferences on disaster mitigation and management.

The main piece of legislation concerning flood emergency management is the Council of Ministers Decree for Civil Defense No 25 of 23/1/1406H (1986). This legislation provides a basic framework defining the composition of the supreme council for civil defense, the tasks that should be performed during a flood disaster and efforts of co-ordination with different parties involved.

The legislation, however, does not specify any major precautions to mitigate flood hazard adverse impacts like limiting new urban development in flood-prone areas or imposing some regulations on newer constructions. It does not also indicate any role assigned to local stakeholders, voluntary associations and local populations who are often the first responders in the event of a disaster. Formal agencies however, tend to lag always behind the local populations.

The legal system maintains the idea that the central government should take the primary responsibility for protecting the public from all aspects of flood hazards, paving the way to a centralized way of management. Many shortcomings are inherent to excessive centralization like delays in disaster response, slow decision taking and organizational problems of aid and recovery procedures which may result in adverse impacts on people and their economic resources. This management approach is elaborated much further in the following paragraphs.

Management: Top-down vs. Bottom-up Approaches

Being a characteristically top down, interventionist approach, the Saudi disaster management strategy consists of deploying physical and human resources from outside the disaster zone. Initiatives are typically technology-centered and driven by outside ‘experts’, giving little interest to local population involvement in the rescue emergency process. However, during the first days before extensive outside help arrive in any disaster-hit area; local people have to face up to their own problems and provide for aid and support to those affected. Waiting for outside help to arrive can produce a delay in disaster mitigation and recovery efforts, leading to consequent loss of human lives and property assets. Integrating the support of informal local community associations in the emergency process in collaboration with formal agencies can be of paramount importance to disaster recovery and response.

Community-based bottom-up approaches can thus, be better suited to deal with flood hazard management as they rely on local population involvement and community capacity. The use of indigenous local knowledge drawn from cyclical disaster events and previous experiences transmitted from one generation to another can make a real difference to disaster management at the local level. Moreover, local people know a great deal about their social and physical environment. Their input would be swiftly geared towards those people most in need and in the areas most affected. Interest should therefore, be directed towards enhancing public participation and local community capacity so that response to the adverse impacts of flood hazards can be prompt and effective.

Many case studies have shown that formal institutions with their conventional solutions and programs have failed to induce local people to participate because these interventions have lacked both the will and the instruments to allow people to use their own knowledge (Tran et al., 2009). This explains in part the limited success of the Saudi conventional approach to disaster response and mitigation as it lacks the integration and enhancement of local community capacity in its emergency planning strategy.

Although recent literature increasingly emphasizes community-based pre-emptive approaches to focus on the root causes of vulnerability to disasters rather than isolated disaster events (Blaikie et al., 1994), the Saudi disaster management strategy still primarily concentrates on the disaster and how to respond to rather than the causes that

have produced it. Here again, attention must be shifted from the disaster per se to its causes and the vulnerabilities the local community suffers from.

Not only does community-based disaster management (CBDM) boost people's ability to live up to the challenges of a disaster event, but it also helps improving relief organization at the local level and assists at drafting the community's own specific management plans to fit the needs of the community's local situation. The outcome of such a bottom-up approach would by far outweigh what might be expected from the top-down approach in use so far in Saudi Arabia.

The management issues abovementioned are not the only ones that have badly affected disaster response and mitigation; other issues related to physical planning and mapping have exacerbated the problem even further.

Poor Planning and Infrastructure

Poor infrastructure has always been blamed for the devastating effects of flash flooding. Although there is host of planning and building codes already specified, the imperfect works of storm sewer ducts or their the absence altogether have been the cause of many devastating flooding impacts. Lack of skills, insufficient financial resources, poor planning and even inexperienced implementation are other causes. The problem is exacerbated by lack of coordination between governments agencies entitled to carry out project realizations. For example, some projects are entrusted with the local municipalities; others with the Ministry of Municipal and Rural Affairs (MOMRA) while some others with the Ministry of Transport, each with its own planning requirements and implementation procedures. In such a case, coordination is often made difficult and poses questions as to how urban planning decisions are being taken.

In the 2009 Jeddah flooding disaster for example, storm sewer drainage system was imperfect, ducts were missing, and most old tunnels were constructed in a way that they follow the topographic slope from east (highland) to west (lowland) towards the Red sea. This direction is obviously the natural direction of flood water flows, whereas the right position for those tunnels would have been the opposite direction (orthogonal North-South) (Al-Alami, 2011).

Many cities have adopted an orthogonal plan layout (Fig 1). In sloping areas, water flows would run from uplands to lowlands along the roads. Intercepted by buildings on both sides of the road, flowing waters would gain accelerated force down the hill. The steeper the slope the more devastating the flood currents would be. Moreover, building and population densities tend to be higher at lowlands which results on more people and properties being exposed to the adverse impacts of flooding.

Although urban regulations do not permit any development on valley streams, in practice however, many developers have filled the flood plain to build upon in total transgression of the building code.. Riyadh local authorities however, have lately decided to rehabilitate the natural floodplains especially in places where many parts of old valleys have disappeared to become new built-up areas. This will result in a daunting task of expropriations and drainage projects.

The devastating effects of flash flooding are exacerbated by poorly planned and managed urbanization, urban expansions over flood-prone areas and impervious surfaces of urban streets, car parking and other paved areas. These features combined with poor drainage networks make urban areas very susceptible to flash flooding as the runoff flows at high speed, carrying large amounts of debris of all sorts, including rubbles, trees and even cars. In a study conducted by the Ministry of Municipal and Rural Affairs (MOMRA) on flood disaster risks in Saudi cities using variables based on meteorological data, current built up area and drainage network coverage, showed that among 29 cities listed, many of them have less than 50% drainage network coverage. The three largest cities in the country (Riyadh, Makkah and Jeddah) have topped the ranking list (Riyadh Newspaper Workshop, 2013).

Physical vulnerabilities to flood disasters are often intertwined with social vulnerabilities. To be able to spot the vulnerabilities in any disaster-prone zone, planners and managers must use disaster risk assessment mapping. This issue of mapping disaster vulnerability is further explained in the following section.

Fig 1: Google-earth views of orthogonal plan layouts for the two major cities: Riyadh (a) and Jeddah (b)

Mapping Disaster Vulnerability

Disaster vulnerability affects certain categories of people more than others. People who tend to be at greater risk in a flood disaster incident like frail people, the poor, and the elderly and migrant minorities should be identified. The areas where they tend to concentrate and the hazard-prone zones should also be determined and mapped. It is crucial therefore, for planners to establish community vulnerability and risk assessment maps and maintain databases reflecting the extent to which people and property assets are vulnerable to the adverse effects of flood hazards. Mapping disaster vulnerability (risk maps) can help policy makers and planners spot areas of highest susceptibility and impact. It also allows managers to survey rapidly the needs and opportunities for mitigation (Twigg, 2004), set up proper planning actions and allocate adequate resources for disaster preparedness (Morrow, 1999). Although the decision to evacuate people at risk should be considered as a last resort, frail people and those with disabilities or reduced mobility should be mapped so that they can be easily identified and evacuated whenever this option becomes necessary.

Risk maps should also be made easy to interpret and simple to read and understand by both technical and non-technical individuals. The mapping of both social and physical vulnerabilities helps identify the most vulnerable people and places in a flood-risk area. When coupled with documentation and mapping of flood hazard proneness and resources availability, it would help enhancing the community capacity and mobilizing population involvement which leads to expedite recovery and prevent loss of life.

The Saudi strategy's attention, as is the case with many rescue agencies, revolves more around the disaster and its impacts rather than the vulnerabilities of the people affected. Heijmans (2004) argues against this approach adopted by disaster response agencies in which they tend to increasingly focus on physical and economic aspects of vulnerability. He stresses addressing the social and political aspects of vulnerability in order to make a lasting impact on overall vulnerability to disaster. Flood vulnerability mapping can be an important tool to provide information not only about the current state of flood-risk areas but also about inundation risk areas, populations at risk, the past flood track records, population losses and property damages, potential evacuation routes and places etc. Such information about flooding and vulnerable elements should be made available to all parties concerned like local stakeholders, local government, aid agencies and local people. Not only can this approach specifically reveal the social and physical vulnerabilities in the disaster-hit areas, but it will allow setting up priorities for disaster response, and rescue operations.

Flood planning and mapping in an area can be made highly effective by means of vulnerability zoning, in which areas are classified from higher to lower levels of vulnerability, as shown in figure 4. The purpose behind the production of such vulnerability maps is to better comprehend and communicate flood extent and flood characteristics such as water depths and velocity. This further helps in the proposition of effective flood control measures, evacuation planning, flood warning and, flood defense mechanisms. Multiple stakeholders like city managers, urban planners, emergency responders and the community at risk can use hazard maps in planning long term flood hazard mitigation, preparation, response, and recovery measures.

Local knowledge in disaster management should also be documented and transferred into maps and be made available to all parties concerned with flooding emergency process. It must be stressed that the issue of mapping is not limited to expert agencies; local communities should be involved in the mapping process, may be through

interacting with online mapping means and open source mapping technologies. Local mapping contribution, can be seen as a bottom up participative approach. Such maps would reveal the community's own situation together with its own physical and social vulnerabilities better than any other expert map.

To measure community vulnerability to flooding, a whole gamut of variables in the area of occurrence should be considered. Data for variables like poverty; poor housing and living conditions; population characteristics; levels of preparedness and awareness; population densities; development of squatter settlements in hazard prone zones; poor maintenance of drainage structures; limitations in early warning systems, should be first gathered and properly processed before undertaking any analysis and mapping within the GIS environment.

Integration of GIS and Mapping Techniques

Whether the focus is on the probable effects of flooding, the identification of the best possible evacuation alternatives, or the recovery planning, the issue is related to the spatial distribution of vulnerable elements, rescue routes and redeveloping areas. Since the spatial component is always present, the integration of powerful spatial analytics using GIS capabilities and mapping techniques can be of paramount importance to support the process of analysis and decision making in emergency planning and management. However, the serious challenge in this application is the lack of appropriate data and the weakness of the available data in terms of validity and reliability. Better decisions cannot be achieved without good maps, and appropriate mapping cannot be realized without good data.

GIS powerful modeling tools and capabilities allow for producing flood hazard-prone areas (risk maps). Appropriate modeling of flood disaster for planning, mapping and management requires integrating quality and updated spatial and non-spatial data. Data, for example, about spatial distribution of residents, their densities, their socioeconomic status and their attributes must be carefully collected. It is therefore critical to first gather information about the road network, its capacity and layout, and its usability during the event of a disaster. Once appropriate spatial and non-spatial data inserted into the GIS software, decision makers would find it extremely useful. For example, it would be possible to get exact information about both the location and count, say for example, of people to be evacuated, the number of vehicles or buses for transportation, the escape routes and shelters with their capacity and the catering facilities and hospitals with the number of beds available, estimated loss of lives, people injured, properties damaged and businesses disrupted. Furthermore, summary statistics and indices can be generated on-the-fly. Diagnostic analysis can also be performed; e.g., all information about objects or items that cannot be evacuated for one reason or another can also be identified. Such an assessment can help making recommendations for prevention, preparedness and response. It also allows providing a sound basis for the planning and allocation of funds and other resources.

However, areas at risk of flooding are not static but dynamic in nature. Decision-makers need up-to-date information in order to allocate resources appropriately. Continuous data and map updating as well as monitoring are therefore, important for proper flood risk planning and management. This task is increasingly made possible through the integration of various data acquisition, analysis, and mapping technologies such as Remote Sensing (RS), Geographic Information System (GIS) and Global Positioning Systems (GPS). These technologies have already proved to be an essential component of disaster planning and mapping processes. When used properly, they can help tremendously improving the quality of data collected.

Status of data and mapping

In Saudi Arabia, data and information vary in source, form, size, and quality. Both the Presidency of Meteorology and Environment (PME) and the Bureau of General Statistics and Information (BGS) collect and manage data for their own purposes (meteorological and environmental data for the former and demographic, economic and housing data for the latter). However, both show some reluctance to share their raw data. The process of map production is therefore made a thorny issue because raw data are not easily accessible. King Abdulaziz City for Science and Technology (KACST) has the mandate to acquire and manage remote sensing data.

The General Commission for Survey (GCS) is the agency responsible for the production of topographic map series starting from the 1:25000 scale and smaller. Larger scale maps and data intended mainly for civic planning purposes are produced by the Ministry of Municipalities and Rural Affairs (MOMRA). Other government authorities (e.g., Ministry of Transport) produce maps and collect data for their own use based on various data sources. Different data sources often lead to data inconsistencies causing a serious harm to the process of disaster risk mapping that requires reliable, valid, and standardized data. This probably explains why different government departments use different base maps.

As to the the availability of national risk maps, only three public maps were found. The World Health Organization produced in 2010 a small-scale flood hazard map for the entire Saudi Arabia (Fig 2). The Jeddah Regional Climate Center (JRCC) provided on its website another map (Fig 3) with the association of the Presidency of Meteorology and Environment (PME). It was dated on 11/20/2013 and showed current levels of meteorological hazards. Although such maps are helpful as a warning aid, they cannot be of great help when dealing with flood disaster planning and management at the local level. The Saudi Geological Survey (SGS) has also drawn its own map to represent geological hazards in the country. From the public use perspective, this map is difficult to read because it is just a small image on the SGS website.

Conflicting numbers as to the rainfall amounts or estimates of disaster losses is another issue in data reliability and validity. For example, rainfall estimates are recorded either by direct monitoring or through statistical means. They come from various government and non-government sources, such as the Ministry of Water and Electricity, the Ministry of Municipal and Rural Affairs. Such sources conduct their own research and monitoring activities, meteorology services, etc. It is therefore difficult to rely on inconsistent set of data for disaster management and mapping. The lack of a single agency to rely on for the provision of appropriate and timely information and reliable data to government departments, the media and the public has made the problem even acute. Unfortunately, this is precisely the case with the Saudi context where data collection about flood hazards is very poor. There is not enough data, and the quality of what is available is often questionable which does not help making good planning decisions or management plans for flash flooding disasters.

By examining the digital online data content uploaded and managed by government departments, it appeared that there is a substantial amount of data and information available to the public, though with varying details. However, as noted above, raw data are not available, incomplete, or inaccessible through these websites. From a technical evaluation perspective, a relatively recent study (Al-Hazzani, 2009) evaluated a sample of government sites. The study found that there are limitations in the use of data identifiers (Data descriptors) compared to global standards. Uses of these identifiers do not accurately reflect the huge content within the websites tested.. The study recommended redesigning or restructuring the websites according to a well-defined (standard) metadata specification to ensure greatest exposure of the website content to the public.

In our search for published flood hazard maps of any Saudi city, none was found that contains all the required information about flooding characteristics like water depth, velocity, duration, and locations for evacuation and gathering places or flood-prone areas or those exposed to higher flood risks. Apart from research endeavors within academic institutions, no vulnerability assessment mapping, be it social or physical vulnerability, was systematically undertaken. Furthermore, researchers interested in disaster planning find it difficult to access to raw data from government agencies. Even when access to such data is provided, researchers have to build their own databases from numerous sources including their own observations.

Fig.2: An example of world organization-based flood hazard maps for Saudi Arabia. A small scale map for the entire Saudi Arabia produced, in raster form, by the World Health Organization, 2010. According to the WHO flood hazard index as shown in the legend, most of the country land lies within the first two classes.

Fig.3: Current Levels of Meteorological Dangers Map of Saudi Arabia on 11/20/2013. Legend symbols, right, refer to danger levels (4), the green symbol denotes the least level of danger, the red symbol denotes maximum danger implying there is a severe metrological condition or flood. On this date, there were heavy rain and floods in many places especially in Riyadh (in the middle), however the symbol used on the map should be red for Riyadh. (Source: PME, <http://jrcc.sa/ew/index.php>) Legend translation added.

Fig. 4: An example of a university-based research on predicting flood hazards. Predicted flood losses based on the ESRI's Flood Risk Factors Model applied to a typical flooded area in the southwestern region of Saudi Arabia (Al-Ahamadi and Al-Ghamdi, 2011).

Pre-event vs. Post-event Disaster Mitigation

The literature defines four main phases for flood disaster planning and management. They are mitigation, preparation, response and recovery. The first two phases are related to the pre-event whereas the last two characterize the post-event disaster. The interest in Saudi Arabia is geared more towards the post-event that is response and recovery. Prior preparations seem to be relegated further down the priority list. Little programs have been arranged to increase public awareness to deal with flash flood disasters when they occur. Education for example is an essential means to increase such awareness. The Saudi general curricula however, lack any standard and consistent materials or exercises about what to do in the event of a flood hazard. Although some emergency evacuation drills are conducted in some schools, they are mainly related to fire disasters. In their study, Momani and Salmi (2012) found the 514 surveyed schools totally unprepared to deal with other future disasters but fire outbreaks.

Even at the university level, research and academic programs on emergency planning and disaster management are lacking. Among the twenty-five universities in the country, offering hundreds of programs in different fields, only one diploma program under the auspices of King Abdulaziz University in Jeddah was designed for emergency planning. Research on this subject is somehow lacking or not enough to say the least. Few research chairs, along with research centers, were established within the last ten years. In any case, government agencies are not fully aware of the research undertaken on the subject of emergency planning and disaster management because of lack of cooperation, coordination or information flows and exchanges between research centers and other concerned recipients of such works. In some cases, being written in English, the research output or reports produced by the research centers can be seen as an inaccessible source by other institutions and the general public.

The focus on post-event disaster is not enough; pre-event mitigation must be considered if sound flood disaster planning and management measures are to be set up. Raising flash flooding awareness and preparedness could be among such measures.

Flash Flooding Disaster Awareness and Preparedness

Raising flood disaster awareness and preparedness among populations at risk is an important tool for flood hazards mitigation and response. The awareness and preparedness to a flood hazard consists of getting ready to dealing with both the direct and indirect impacts of a disaster. By direct impacts is meant the rescue of at risk population and property protection. Indirect impacts however, refer to disturbances caused to the affected community and disruptions to its businesses. People and communities may go through a lot of hardship in getting on with their daily routine lives if their businesses are not restored once the disaster is over. It is imperative therefore to pay as much attention and be prepared to respond to people rescue and relief as to business restitution and continuity. Core response in the Saudi context tends to be more focused upon the direct impacts of a disaster like loss of lives, injuries, and property damages. Indirect impacts such as business interruption or disruption are not given much attention.

As mentioned above, local residents are the first to have to deal with the effects of flood hazard and emergency, a great deal of effort should be made to raise and maintain public awareness to improve community preparedness to any eventual flood event. For that, an effective warning system with appropriate lead time for flash flooding is critical as it empowers individuals and communities to respond promptly and properly to floods reducing the risk of death, injury, property loss or damage. To maintain pre-flood awareness and preparedness, it is crucial to conduct training drills and exercises on a regular basis. Here again the dissemination of the right information in time and the provision of vulnerability maps to the community at large and local stakeholders can increase awareness and mitigate a great deal of the disaster adverse impacts.

Everything must be planned for and organized well in advance to be able to properly deal with the flood hazard when it occurs. At this stage government agencies and all relevant stakeholders must be aware of their share of the job, their responsibilities and their roles during a flood hazard. Such preparedness can help mitigate the disaster, avoid major disruptions and restart businesses once again relatively quickly. At the preparation stage, stakeholders should be organized into working committees. Once all the information disseminated, roles and duties defined for all stakeholders, the planning for emergencies can then be launched. It is important for all stakeholders to have clear roles and responsibilities during the event of a flood disaster. This can help avoid any duplication or overlap of duties and hence waste of precious resources and time.

The experience gained so far in dealing with flood disasters in Saudi Arabia has revealed little coordination between different parties. Although the local emergency committee has to convene at least once a year to discuss coordination and organizational issues, such meetings are neither regular nor taken seriously by the concerned parties. Other programs can be designed to improve the level of preparedness among all parties involved in facing up to the challenge of the flash flood hazard. These programs can include training, expertise and best practices exchange, simulation exercises, etc. A centralized unit or cell for disaster analysis, mapping and planning can be of paramount importance. This point is further explained next.

A Centralized Geo-Database for Disaster Management

As stated earlier, different data sources and diverse geo-databases may well lead to varied spatial information products. The creation and use of a central national geo-database is therefore, an urgent necessity to overcome the abovementioned mapping issues. Alternatively, each administrative region or province should be provided with its own reliable, complete, and updated geo-database, as is the case with the new emergency management center in the city of Jeddah, which is a project underway.

Such databases are to be hosted within a centralized unit for flood disaster analysis, planning, management and mapping. Although a centre for flood analysis at the national level is yet to be established, some precursor signs of its creation can be noticed in Jeddah and Makkah where an early warning system is being set up (e.g. Jeddah Regional Climate Centre - JRCC).

It is therefore imperative to establish an emergency center equipped with the latest cutting edge technologies for data handling, processing and mapping and disaster analysis, planning and management. If establishing a national or provincial center proved difficult, then each major city, at least, should have one such emergency operation center which should act as a cell for flood risk analysis, preventive information collection and warning dissemination. It should be composed of local civil protection committee with representatives of different sectors and of local associations and governmental departments. It should be responsible for information gathering, coordination and documentation on flood hazards and disaster management in the area concerned. Local stakeholders should be designated and called upon to have their say in disaster planning and management. This should help developing stronger linkages between the research community and those in charge of the management and rescue operations. The creation of a center for data handling, processing and mapping is therefore critical for flood risk planning and management. Lack of such centers in any city can have some detrimental effects on disaster response and management.

CONCLUSION

The paper examined various issues pertaining to the current practice of disaster planning, management and mapping in Saudi Arabia. The focus was on flash flood disasters for three reasons: (a) they are the predominant type of natural disaster in the country; (b) their occurrence is becoming more frequent; and (c) their severity and their devastating impacts on people and properties are getting more destructive. Effects of this disaster in Saudi Arabia in terms of losses and destruction raise many issues. A 30mm flash rainfall can be an uncommon event with disastrous consequences in Saudi Arabia. Some light was shed on the local experience regarding disaster planning, management and mapping. Some deficiencies in practice were highlighted and some necessary corrections for a better disaster management and mapping were suggested.

It is vital to have a single reference database and base maps easily accessible and readily available to all government departments, scientific community and the general public to rely upon for data processing and disaster analysis and mapping. Experience has shown that working with disseminated and fragmented data impedes the processes of disaster planning and management.

Reliance only on government institutions and interventions for flood disaster planning and management has shown many drawbacks and limitations. Coordination among government bodies and local community associations is vital both for pre-disaster event preparedness as well as for post-disaster response and mitigation. Local populations and stakeholders should also be involved in the process as their input in terms of accumulated knowledge about cyclical disaster events and social and physical vulnerabilities can be critical. Such knowledge should also be mapped and integrated into GIS platforms.

The literature on planning and management models is abundant. However, before proposing specific models, two tasks must first be achieved: (1) the creation of a central national geo-database, (2) the establishment of either a national emergency management center, or at least local centers in each administrative region. Such centers should

be concerned with all stages of hazard management and planning and equipped with appropriate technologies and experts.

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